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Abstract: This report documents (1) the process of consultation with the communities targeted at finding use cases for the tools for enlarging their scope and applicability e.g. processing new data-types and offering more appropriate data processing, (2) the resulting implementation actions and future implementation planning, (3) repercussions of the implementations plans with regard to governance and sustainability for these services, and (4) the accompanying activities of documentation and engagement with end users.

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Executive Summary

SSHOC Task 3.6 (Making Data Re-usable and Actionable) focuses on two services originally from the CLARIN infrastructure domain, which in discussion and collaboration with the SSHOC communities are generalised and adapted to serve the broader Humanities and Social Sciences. Specifically with the purpose of facilitating better sharing and re-use of data and services in innovative ways.

Those services are the SSH Switchboard also known as the CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard and the SSH Virtual Collection Registry also known as the CLARIN Virtual Collection Registry (VCR).

In this deliverable the task team reports on (1) the process of consultation with the communities targeted at finding use cases for the tools for enlarging their scope and applicability e.g. processing new data-types and offering more appropriate data processing, (2) the resulting implementation actions and future implementation planning, (3) repercussions of the implementation plans with regard to governance and sustainability for these services, and (4) the accompanying activities of documentation and engagement with end-users.

The report references other documents and milestones (for a detailed list consult the introduction) and links to related activities, not directly related with the Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry. In this sense this task pursued the strategic objective to better connect and raise visibility of SSH resources and services, implied in the work package title “Lifting Technologies and Services into the SSH Cloud”.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AAI	Authentication Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CLARIAH-DE	German research infrastructure merger of CLARIN-D and DARIAH-DE
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ERA	European Research Area
ERIHs	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FDO	Fair Digital Object
LR Switchboard	Language Resource Switchboard
LTP	Long Term Preservation
MP	SSH Open Marketplace
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PID	Persistent Identifier
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
VC	Virtual Collection
VCR	Virtual Collection Registry

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Introduction

This document describes the status of the work done in the SSHOC project, particularly in task 3.6 “Making Data Re-usable and Actionable”, with respect to two tools originally developed for the CLARIN infrastructure: “The Language Resource Switchboard” (Switchboard¹) and “The CLARIN Virtual Collection Registry” (VCR²). The goal of SSHOC task 3.6 is to investigate and effectuate the generalisation and use of the Switchboard and the VCR in the SSHOC partner infrastructures DARIAH, CESSDA and EHRIS. The team discussed with those communities practical use cases and derived requirements for the tools that would allow for broader use beyond the CLARIN community.

The Switchboard is a tool that enables advanced human actionability of embedded links to data resources in all types of web interfaces (e.g., a research data repository or data catalogue). The Switchboard brokers and matches between the resources of a specific data-type and language, and web applications that can do something useful with such resources for the user. Although the brokering function is automatic, i.e., filtering metadata descriptions of services on the basis of resource data type and content language, the user has to initiate the execution of any service by selecting a service from the picklist presented by the Switchboard. A description for the original CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard is available³.

The VCR permits users to create and register virtual collections (VC) which are sets of references to resources from different repositories together with some descriptive metadata describing the collection itself. A PID is then issued for the collection that can be used for citation purposes. The original use of this tool was to provide users with a way to cite many different resources with a single citation, but meanwhile its potential scope has been extended, for a large part also within the SSHOC project. An extensive VCR factsheet for researchers is being worked on.

This deliverable follows on a number of earlier reports on achieved Milestones:

- MS9 Inventory of services, tools and domain of actionable data-types, *not published*
- MS12 Implementation plan SSHOC Switchboard and VCR Services, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4681041](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681041)

and a number of related documents:

- Collaborative Use Cases between SSH Open Marketplace and the Language Resource Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry. Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4442320](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4442320) and a later published addendum of this document under DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5215987](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5215987)

¹ CLARIN Switchboard: <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/> (accessed Oct 2021)

² CLARIN Virtual Collection Registry: <https://collections.clarin.eu/public?0> (accessed Oct 2021)

³ Claus Zinn. 2016b. The CLARIN language resource switchboard. https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/zinn-CLARIN2016_paper_26.pdf. Abstract for the CLARIN 2016 Annual Conference.

- VCR summary document published on Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5535817](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5535817)

Since this deliverable is the first and only deliverable of task 3.6 and in order to provide (as much as possible) a self-contained complete text, this deliverable also covers information provided already in the previously mentioned documents.

The reader might notice some inconsistencies regarding the names that are used for the Switchboard and VCR in different documents. This is related to the branding discussion that is at the moment of writing partly still ongoing. The intention is to generalise both tools for use by the whole SSH, but then, should the names still contain “CLARIN” as the community of origin? The same problem arises if SSHOC, which considerably contributed to the further development of the tools, lends its name to these tools as SSHOC Switchboard and SSHOC VCR and then ceases to exist after the duration of the project. These are difficult decisions and, in the end, the decision was to be pragmatic and use in the documents:

- Switchboard instead of CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard, since it is no longer specific for Language Resources, and it is not specific for CLARIN,
- Virtual Collection Registry, since it is not CLARIN specific.

Only when the role of the originator community needs emphasis the name of CLARIN is prepended, and in other CLARIN specific documents the name CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard (LR Switchboard) is continued.

Both the Switchboard and the VCR were originally developed in the context of other national and European projects. They were also integrated in the EOSC Marketplace onboarding process in the EOSC-Hub project as thematic services. See the Switchboard and VCR registrations⁴ in the marketplace.

Community use case discussions

An important and labour-intensive part of the SSHOC T3.6 work was to discuss the generalisation of the Switchboard and VCR for other communities. How can both services be used by the whole SSH community? Together with the SSHOC communities use-cases were worked out that would firstly identify how the Switchboard and VCR could be useful for their respective researchers and secondly determined what extensions or modifications might be necessary for those use cases.

Discussions took part in two stages, conveying sometimes new concepts and their potential application such as what is a virtual collection and intensive brainstorming of how Switchboard and VCR could be used as stand-alone tools by researchers but more important what would be beneficial integrations of

⁴ The Switchboard in the EOSC Marketplace: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/language-resource-switchboard> and the Virtual Collection Registry in the EOSC Marketplace: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/virtual-collection-registry> (accessed Oct 2021)

the tools with existing infrastructure components that the SSHOC stakeholders already operate for their researchers e.g., catalogues and repository systems.

Underlying this approach is the idea that the research-infrastructures can profit from sharing and integrating their tools and services in a way that predominantly leaves the responsibility for operating and maintaining the tools and services with their originating community, and a lightweight cross-community integration of each other's services has a multiplying effect both in delivering functionality to the users and cost-saving.

The discussions with selected partners and communities are documented in this paper and intended to be continued after the SSHOC project, for instance within the EOSC and ERIC context. The project served as valuable means to establish close ties between research infrastructure institutions, which are in the long run beneficial for the European Research Area as a whole.

Note that the VCR and Switchboard software are also subject to normal maintenance and some functionality gets improved or added that has no direct relation to the SSHOC project. Such items are not explicitly listed here. It may be mentioned however, that such development on the services is made in a transparent and sustainable way, using a code repository at GitHub⁵.

DARIAH-DE use case

During the German CLARIAH-DE project the data collections behind DARIAH-DE⁶ and CLARIN-D⁷ have been linked with one another and made available for cross-searching, at various levels of integration⁸. DARIAH-DE-related repositories have become CLARIN Data Centres and vice versa CLARIN collections (e.g., the FCVS) have been made searchable through the DARIAH Federation Architecture. In this context DARIAH-DE is used interchangeably for CLARIAH-DE. However, it is important to note that this does not include the ERIC level, i.e., DARIAH-EU.

⁵ VCR Github repository: <https://github.com/clarin-eric/VirtualCollectionRegistry> and the Switchboard Github repository: <https://github.com/clarin-eric/Switchboard> (accessed Oct 2021)

⁶ Heike Neuroth, Stefan Schmunk, Mirjam Blümm, Andrea Rapp, Fotis Jannidis, Dirk Wintergrün, Ulrich Schwardmann und Peter Gietz (Hg.): *Bibliothek Forschung und Praxis*. Band 40, Heft 2; Sonderheft: Digitalität in den Geistes- und Kulturwissenschaften am Beispiel der digitalen Forschungsinfrastruktur DARIAH-DE. Juli 2016, DOI: [10.1515/bfp-2016-0019](https://doi.org/10.1515/bfp-2016-0019)

⁷ CLARIN-D German website: <https://www.clarin-d.net/en/> (accessed Oct 2021)

⁸ See Thomas Eckart, Tobias Gradl, Robin Jegan, Eliza Margaretha, Antonina Werthmann, Felix Helfer, Stefan Buddenbohm. "[CLARIAH-DE Cross-Service Search: Prospects and Benefits of Merging Subject-specific Services](#)". DARIAH-DE Working Papers Nr. 41. Göttingen: DARIAH-DE, 2021. URN: [urn:nbn:de:gbv:7-dariah-2021-1-9](https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:gbv:7-dariah-2021-1-9) accessed Oct 2021)

Virtual Collection Registry

With the DARIAH-DE Data Federation Architecture⁹ and the included Collection Registry¹⁰ a similar service exists already in CLARIAH-DE, although its collection members are limited to a fixed set of repositories. Therefore, the DARIAH-DE VCR use case revolves more around interoperability and enhanced user experience (more research data and services available) and not around directly integrating the VCR in the DARIAH-DE portfolio. Basic interoperability between the two communities was already provided due to previous collaborations and recently the merger project CLARIAH-DE. Basic interoperability depends on shared use of standards, protocols and collaboration agreements e.g. TEI as text file format and protocols such as OAI-PMH for metadata harvesting, SAML based AAI and an agreement to harvest one another's metadata.

Apart from basic interoperability some specific integration options of the VCR in DARIAH-DE are:

1. Enhancement of the CLARIN VCR in a way that it may access the DARIAH Generic Search and by this acquires humanities-related data. In this use case, the DFA could be understood as the humanities interface of the VCR.
2. Enhancement of the CLARIN VCR in a way that it is able to save search queries to the DARIAH Generic Search and is able to aggregate them instantly. An extension of the shopping-basket use case [CESSDA or Shopping-basket use case](#)

In terms of the specific functionalities as mentioned by the other communities in this document, CLARIAH-DE would request the following ones (partly already implemented):

1. Expansion of the data domain available to the VCR
 - a. Testing for additional data sets (e.g., combined DARIAH and other SSH domains). This could be done along disciplinary or data domains (e.g., collections, lexicographic resources, editions).
 - b. This could include a showcase demonstrating the user how a user may add resources from other domains. Such a showcase could make use of the DARIAH-DE data space.
2. Personal space
 - a. Sharing of VCs: users should be able to access VCs from other creators and should be able to copy them to their own space (implemented).
3. Citing of VCs
 - a. VCs should be easily citable via PIDs (implemented).

Apart from the above mentioned specific use cases other scenarios emerged in the discussion:

⁹ The DARIAH-DE Data Federation Architecture and its constituting components: <https://de.dariah.eu/en/data-federation-architecture> (accessed Oct 2021)

¹⁰ The DARIAH-DE Collection Registry as similar service: <https://colreg.de.dariah.eu/colreg-ui/> (accessed Oct 2021)

1. Review of the CLARIN VCR API and the RDA Collection API and evaluation of possible acquisitions enhancing the VCR. In view of the problems getting developer resources this activity had to be postponed beyond the SSHOC scope. Integration with other repository APIs such as Fair Digital Object (FDO) API may need to be prioritised.
2. Work on a possible VCR extension of the SSH Open Marketplace, e.g., that VCs may contain items from the marketplace.

Switchboard

Regarding the implementation of useful links from DARIAH-DE resources to the Switchboard, manifold options are possible as the Switchboard offers a broad range of tools and services suitable also for the user community of DARIAH-DE which has an arts and humanities background. Although most of the listed tools and services are language processing related, a basic applicability is thinkable and would likely be appreciated by the users.

The basic usage scenario would be to allow the user, who has encountered an individual research data set in a DARIAH resource (e.g., the TextGrid Digital Library or the DARIAH-DE repository) to explore tool options. The following use cases have been discussed:

1. Invocation of the Switchboard from a DARIAH-DE resource based on MIME Type: If resources in the source repository - for instance the TextGrid Digital Library¹¹ - the Switchboard could be invoked from the individual resource site. This use case has been sufficiently implemented during SSHOC (see screenshot of the function below). The same functionality has been implemented for the DARIAH-DE repository¹², which will likely gain relevance in the future as one of the research data repositories of CLARIAH-DE.
2. The Switchboard can determine the data-type of a resource if it gets the resource URI. The user can quite conveniently click on the ‘Switchboard’ invocation button and gets the instant results from the Switchboard through a pop-up. The user does not leave the original resource in this scenario. The displayed results are based on the file’s MIME type and will be a selection from the Switchboard tool inventory or the current beta of the Switchboard.
3. Switchboard as ingested source in DARIAH-DE: This use case describes the inclusion of the Switchboard tool inventory on the individual tool level in a DARIAH resource, here the “Diensteliste” (=service inventory) of the CLARIAH-DE website¹³: (see screenshot of the function below) Please note, that this is a prototypical implementation and will likely change soon. This leverages the visibility and uptake of the CLARIN resources. The Switchboard tool inventory¹⁴

¹¹ For instance: <https://hdl.handle.net/11858/00-1734-0000-0002-3D6F-8> (accessed Oct 2021)

¹² See the Switchboard integration in the DARIAH-DE Repository:
<https://trep.de.dariah.eu/1.0/dhcrud/21.T11991/0000-0011-B8C6-E/index> (accessed Oct 2021)

¹³ <https://www.clariah.de/ueber-uns/diensteliste> (accessed Oct 2021)

¹⁴ See <https://beta-switchboard.clarin.eu/tools> (accessed Oct 2021)

consists of 73 tools for language related research data (November 2020). It is very likely that the enhanced tool inventory visibility will be taken to the next level within the NFDI, the German National Research Data Infrastructure. Text+ as a consortium with a substantial contribution by CLARIAH-DE will very likely consider the Switchboard tool inventory as a useful offering to its users.

The screenshot displays the TextGrid Repository interface. At the top left is the TextGrid logo (an owl) and the text 'TextGrid Repository'. To the right is a search bar with the placeholder 'Suchbegriff' and a magnifying glass icon. Further right are links for 'Regal 0' and 'English'. Below the search bar are dropdown menus for 'Inhalte' and 'Dokumentation'. The main content area is divided into a left sidebar and a main text area. The sidebar contains sections: 'Metadaten' (Dateityp: text/xml, PID: hdl:11858/00-1734-0000-0002-3D6F-8, Zitationsvorschlag), 'Herunterladen' (Objekt (TEI), Metadaten (XML), Tech. Metadaten (XML), Plain Text (txt), E-Book (epub), HTML, ZIP), 'Werkzeug' (Voyant, Annotate, Switchboard), and 'Inhaltsverzeichnis' (Ida Boy-Ed). The main text area shows a breadcrumb trail: 'Boy-Ed, Ida > Essays > Lübeck als Geistesform > Lübeck als Geistesform'. The title is 'Ida Boy-Ed Lübeck als Geistesform'. The text describes a speech by Thomas Mann in 1926 and discusses the author's relationship to his hometown of Lübeck.

Figure 1: The Switchboard integration in the user interface of the TextGrid repository¹⁵

¹⁵ Accessible here: <https://hdl.handle.net/11858/00-1734-0000-0002-3D70-2> (accessed Oct 2021)

Figure 2: The Diensteliste (services list) on the CLARIAH-DE website as demonstrator¹⁶

ARCHE use case

ARCHE¹⁷ is a repository for research data from humanities disciplines run by the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage of the Austrian Academy of Sciences (ACDH-CH OEAW). It currently contains around 25 top collections with altogether more than 76 thousand resources of a wide variety of formats, data-types, predominantly (historical) texts encoded in TEI and images.

ARCHE has been integrated both with the Switchboard and the VCR. Specifically, this integration allows users to pass on TEI-conformant resources to the Switchboard and make any of the resources in the repository part of a new or an existing virtual collection. The Switchboard integration is considered stable and available in the ARCHE production instance while the VCR integration is still in the testing phase and available only in the ARCHE development instance. The Switchboard and the VCR can both be called from the ARCHE GUI¹⁸ (and the Switchboard dissemination can be also requested through the REST API¹⁹).

The integration of the Switchboard has been done by defining it as a so-called ARCHE dissemination service, a generic extension mechanism built into the ARCHE architecture, originally intended to allow the presentation of archived resources in various output formats or forms. It turned out that this

¹⁶ Accessible here: <https://www.clariah.de/ueber-uns/diensteliste> (accessed Oct 2021)

¹⁷ ARCHE (A Resource Centre for the Humanities): <https://arche.acdh.oew.ac.at/>

¹⁸ Example resource: <https://hdl.handle.net/21.11115/0000-000C-2037-2>

¹⁹ Example call: <https://hdl.handle.net/21.11115/0000-000C-2037-2@format=Processing%20data>

mechanism - relying on calling stand-alone services with reference to raw data as parameter - is compatible with/identical to the way the Switchboard service should be called, thus integrating the Switchboard boiled down to configuring yet another dissemination service.

This required two rules to be defined. First, the matching rule selecting ARCHE resources which can be processed by the Switchboard. Second, the redirection rule creates an URL calling the Switchboards for a given ARCHE resource. The matching rule was set to “all resources having the value of the acdh:hasSchema metadata property”²⁰.

The redirection rule uses the https://switchboard.clarin.eu/#/arche/{RES_URI}/{RES_MIME} template where {RES_URI} and {RES_MIME} are substituted with the URL-encoded ARCHE resource URL and ARCHE resource MIME type, respectively. It was decided not to provide the Switchboard with the information about the ARCHE resource’s language as this information is currently inconsistently encoded and requires further consolidation. At the REST API level, the Switchboard service has been assigned the “Processing data” identifier making it possible to request the “dissemination” to Switchboard by passing “format=Processing%20data” parameter²¹.

The ARCHE VCR integration was slightly more complex because the VCR service integration requires HTTP POST requests to be made which is not supported by the ARCHE dissemination services mechanics, the VCR has been integrated in a dedicated way. Nevertheless, the integration was straightforward. The ARCHE GUI sends a HTTP POST request²² with an application/x-www-form-urlencoded body to the VCR submission REST endpoint. The request contains basic ARCHE resource data (PID, label, description). Sending the request causes the redirection of the user to the VCR which takes care of the rest of the process. From the user’s perspective the VCR is being shown just like one more dissemination service available. The VCR integration will be available for all ARCHE resources.

DAI use case: Switchboard for archaeological users

The German Archaeological Institute DAI maintains the iDAI.objects/Arachne database of archaeological objects as a central part of the iDAI.world²³ suite of web services for the archaeologies. An example of an object representation in Arachne is shown in figure 3 below. The DAI use case is to adapt and evaluate the Switchboard potential for Arachne users.

In initial discussions about potential ways the Switchboard could be made useful for users of Arachne — usually coming with an archaeological provenance — and the information systems of the iDAI.world, the

²⁰ Accessible here: <https://www.tei-c.org/release/xml/tei/schema/relaxng/tei.rng>

²¹ Accessible here: <https://hdl.handle.net/21.11115/0000-000C-2037-2@format=Processing%20data> or <https://id.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/uuid/9cb5639c-fae4-ec01-c068-8d842a134c70?format=Processing%20data>

²² See the VCR documentation: <https://github.com/clarin-eric/VirtualCollectionRegistry/blob/master/doc/Integration.md>

²³ iDAI.world website: <https://idai.world> (accessed Oct 2021)

option of using the Switchboard ‘lookup service’ emerged as the most practical one in terms of implementation effort and potential uptake. This particular Switchboard mode of use was at that moment in development and should offer users an opportunity to look up translations of user-selected text fragments or words. In collaboration with the DAI partner it was carefully investigated how this lookup service should be presented to the user and which dictionaries and information sources should be most useful to DAI users. Other use cases were also discussed but eventually dismissed for various reasons.

The Switchboard presence should be experienced as useful and the main question discussing the Switchboard functionality was: what type of translations, dictionary lookups or other processing are useful for the Arachne end-user? The added functionality should have real added value e.g., in the case of the ‘lookup service’ be more convenient than manually copying text and pasting it in a service such as Google Translate in another browser tab. Also, neither the Switchboard’s way of eliciting additional input from the user for the lookup service through a pop-up window, nor the way that the lookup functionality is invoked or configured should be confusing to the users.

The screenshot shows the Arachne web interface for the object 'Brunnen in Schiffsform'. The interface includes a search bar at the top with the text 'Neue Suche'. On the left, there is a map titled 'ORTE' showing the location in Rome, and a 'KATALOGE' section with a button '+ Datensatz zu Katalog hinzufügen'. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Entity-Info:** Entity-ID: 1092860, Kategorie: Einzelobjekte, Seriennummer: 33948.
- Informationen zum Objekt:**
 - Lokalisierung:** Rom, (Roma), Rom (Metropolitanstadt), Italien, Art der Ortsangabe: Fundort. Santa Maria in Domnica, Rom, Italien.
 - Herkunft:** unter Leo X. wurde 1513 das antike Schiffsmodell, das lange vor der Kirche gestanden haben muß und im 15. Jh. bezeugt ist, restauriert und neu aufgestellt; seit 1930 wieder als Brunnenanlage verwendet.
 - Gattung/Funktion/Kulturrepoche:** Inschrift, Bauplastik: Brunnen, zu Monument gehörig: nein, Kulturrepoche: römisch, Gattung: Sonstiges.
 - Datierung:** (empty field)
- Abbildung:** A photograph of the fountain, which is shaped like a ship.
- Verknüpfte Objekte (3):**
 - Inschriften (1)
 - Orte (1)

Figure 3: Object in Arachne: "Brunnen in Schiffsform" (a fountain in Rome, shaped like a ship).

The figure shows two parts of the SSHOC interface. The top part is a 'Resource Switchboard' window. It displays a selected text snippet: 'unter Leo X. wurde 1513 das antike Schiffsmodell, das lange vor der Kirche gestanden haben muß und im 15. Jh. bezugt ist, restauriert und neu aufgestellt; seit 1930 wieder als Brunnenanlage verwendet'. The window shows the mediatype as 'text/plain' and the language as 'German'. Under 'Matching Tools', 'Constituency Parsing' is expanded, showing 'DARIAH DKPro-Wrapper: Constituency Parsing DE' and 'WebLicht Const Parsing DE'. The bottom part of the figure shows a dependency parse graph for the same text. The graph consists of nodes representing words and arcs representing grammatical dependencies. A legend on the left indicates that 'Dependency Parses' are selected for the visualization.

Figure 4: Example: dependency parse for a paragraph

After some experimentation and discussions, it became clear that the original version of the Switchboard was of limited use to archaeologists because it consisted mainly of text analysis tools. Selecting a whole paragraph of text, the text is identified as German, and the Switchboard pop-up window (Fig. 3 left) suggests a list of text analysis services, the example “dependency parse” is shown in figure 4. In general, the use cases for text analysis tools normally do not involve manually selecting text from a website and sending it to the Switchboard but are invoked by selecting a whole text resource (file).

Based on the currently integrated services and available resources it was impossible for now to provide a convincing use case for longer text snippets in Arachne yet. The most interesting possibility that were considered was machine learning translations for Latin and Greek texts. However, this could not be done with the available list of services and would need a parallel development of the accompanying tools. At the time of this discussion, the Switchboard contained only a Dutch-Frisian translation service. It would also require specific language models trained on ancient languages (Greek, Latin) and historic language variants. Another plausible use-case considered, is that of OCR'ed book pages with a service that suggests corrections for e.g., Latin OCR text, including the removal of line breaks. This service would be interesting

to users as well as Arachne as a whole. A complete OCR service for scanned book pages and images of inscriptions where Arachne does not already provide an OCR text turned out to be too complex for the selection of books available in Arachne, namely out-of-copyright books mainly from before 1900, let alone inscriptions that are sometimes hard to decipher even for experts.

The figure shows two screenshots from the iDAI.gazetteer interface. The top screenshot displays search results for 'Samothrace' in Perseus, showing text from Herodotus and the New Testament. The bottom screenshot shows the iDAI.gazetteer interface with a map of Samothrace and a list of results.

Perseus Results:

- Showing 1-10 of 38
- Herodotus, The Histories, Book 2 Chapter 51 Section 3 (2.51.3) translation: +Samothrace (island), Nomos Evrou, Western Thrace, Greece, Europe. Samothrace was formerly inhabited by those Pelasgians who came to live among the Athenians, and it is from them that the Samothracians take their rites.
- New Testament, Acts of the Apostles, Chapter 16 Verse 11 (16.11) translation: Setting sail therefore from Troas, we made a straight course to Samothrace, and the day following to Neapolis;
- Herodotus, The Histories, Book 6 Chapter 47 Section 2 (6.47.2) translation: These Phoenician mines are between the place called Aenyra and Coenyra in +Thasos [24.716.40.783] (deserted settlement), Thasos, Kavalla, Macedonia, Greece, Europe Thasos, opposite +Samothrace (island), Nomos Evrou, Western Thrace, Greece, Europe Samothrace; they are in a great hill that has been dug up in the searching. So much for that. The Thasians at the king's command destroyed their walls and brought all their ships to +Abdera [24.9667.40.9833] (Perseus)

iDAI.gazetteer Results:

Falls within	Tags	Type
> Samothrake 4	> Excavation 1	> Archaeological site 4
> Samothrake 2	> Mountain 1	> Building/Institution 1
> Evros (Periferiakē enótēta)	> Island 1	> Island 1
	> museum 1	> Landform 1
	> polis 1	> Populated place 1

Filter:

- Coordinates
- No coordinates
- Polygon
- No polygon
- Unlocatable

Results Table:

#	Name	Type	URI
1	2070376 Samothrake, Samothraki, Samothrace, Samothrace Island, ... Evros (Periferiakē enótēta), Anatolikē Makedonía kai Thrákē (Periféria), Ellada, Europa, Welt	Island	URI
2	2103265 Samothrake, Samothraki, Samothrace, Samothrace, ... Samothrake, Evros (Periferiakē enótēta), Anatolikē Makedonía kai Thrákē (Periféria), Ellada, Europa, Welt	Archaeological site	URI
3	2306267 Archäologisches Museum, Samothraki Archeological Museum Samothrake, Samothrake, Evros	Location/Institution	URI

Figure 5: Example: Samothrace in iDAI.gazetteer and Perseus

More successfully proved 'lookup services' for individual words up to multi-word terms. It was suggested to create a version of the Switchboard pop-up window and an appropriate list of lookup services that works well on short texts and individual words. Here, some excellent use cases could be identified.

One of these use cases is a gazetteer lookup. Arachne records are already highly linked with other records as well as entries in other services such as the iDAI.gazetteer (see figure 5). However, automated linking to places only works if the information can be found in the designated data fields. If a free text field includes a place name, there is no automated linking. This is where the Switchboard pop-up window proves helpful. It can link the selected word “Samothrace” in figure 5 not only to the iDAI.gazetteer, but also to the Perseus digital library project²⁴ of Greek and Latin texts. Since Samothrace is a Greek place in English spelling, it will be found in English translations of Greek texts in Perseus.

For optimal performance the Switchboard requires and identifies the language of the selected text resources, which is a general challenge for short text snippets. Whereas the phrase “Victory of Samothrace” is still long enough to be recognized as English, for single words the Arachne Switchboard integration is configured to assume they are in German (unless the user specifies a language and overrules this default). The single word “Samothrace” in the example above also gets identified as the default German. Fortunately, both the iDAI.gazetteer and Perseus lookup do not need the language identification information.

Another service where the Switchboard connects Arachne with the iDAI.world’s own services is the iDAI.vocab dictionary of archaeological terms. Linking to the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus²⁵ also serves as a translation service if the German term is found at all. In both cases, this still needs to be fine-tuned since inflected forms such as “antike” will yield few or no results and compound words such as Schiffsmo­dell (ship model) or Brunnenanlage (fountain complex) will yield no results at all. Also, multi-word terms are rarer in German than in English due to different spelling conventions (e.g. stone age versus Steinzeit). In tests it was found that dictionary lookup services will rarely find meaningful results for inputs of more than one German word.

²⁴ Perseus digital library Perseus Hopper 4.0: <https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/> (accessed Oct 2021)

²⁵ Getty Research Institute Art &Architecture Thesaurus: <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/> (accessed Oct 2021)

The screenshot shows the SSHOC Resource Switchboard interface. On the left, there are filters for 'Herkunft', 'Gattung/Funktion/Kulturrep', 'Datierung', 'Material', and 'Erhaltung'. The main search area is titled 'Suchergebnisse' and shows a search for 'restauriert' in German. The search results include a message that the article does not exist in German Wikipedia, a list of search results from Wikisource (Antonio Vivaldi, Panzerkreuzer Potemkin, Berlin - Die Sinfonie der Großstadt, New York Telephone Building), and a Wiktionary entry for 'restauriert' with its pronunciation and grammatical information.

Figure 6: Example: single word “restauriert” in Wikipedia

The German language is a major challenge for the Switchboard lookup service and for Arachne users alike. While the Arachne user interface is available in English, most of the descriptions are in German. This can be illustrated with the relatively simple word form “restauriert” (meaning “restored” as in “some cultural property was restored”) in figure 6. The other available lookup services for the Switchboard Arachne integration are “CLARIN Federated Content Search” and “Wikipedia DE”.

The CLARIN Federated Content Search²⁶ lookup service aggregates results from the combined CLARIN repository specific lookup services, some of which can handle German inflected word forms. One can see word forms such as restaurierten (modern German) or reftauriret (early modern German). However, this handling of German word forms is internal in the individual repository lookup services, not in the Switchboard itself. In the German Wikipedia there is no article called “restauriert” and a search page is displayed instead. Following the link to “restauriert” in the partner project Wiktionary would find the infinitive “restaurieren”, which in turn would lead to the proper Wikipedia page “Restaurierung”, but most users would find this too tedious.

²⁶ The CLARIN Federated Content Search: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/federated-content-search-clarin-fcs> (accessed Oct 2021)

WIKIPEDIA
Die freie Enzyklopädie

Hauptseite
Themenportale
Zufälliger Artikel

Mitmachen

Artikel verbessern
Neuen Artikel anlegen
Autorenportal
Hilfe
Letzte Änderungen
Kontakt
Spenden

Werkzeuge

Links auf diese Seite
Änderungen an verlinkten Seiten
Spezialseiten
Permanenter Link
Seiteninformationen
Artikel zitieren
Wikidata-Datenobjekt

Drucken/exportieren

Restaurierung

Als **Restaurierung** bezeichnet man bei Kulturgütern die Wiederherstellung eines alten Zustands, welcher oft im Laufe der Zeit verloren gegangen ist. Die an einer Restaurierung zu beteiligenden Fachgebiete richten sich nach den zu restaurierenden Objekten (z. B. **Baudenkmale, Tafelbilder, Wandmalereien, archäologische Funde, Musikinstrumente, Oldtimer, Filme**), den verwendeten Materialien (**Holz, Textilien, Malfarben, Stein, Keramik, Papier, Leder, Metall, Glas**) und den angewendeten Techniken.

Neben der *akademischen Restaurierung* ist der Bereich der *handwerklichen Restaurierung* als rein beruflich gebildeter, wirtschaftlich orientierter Tätigkeitsbereich im **Handwerk** etabliert. Insbesondere in der **Altbausanierung** und **Baudenkmalpflege**, aber auch in der Objektrestaurierung (**Musikinstrumente, Bücher, Archivalien, Fahrzeuge** und andere technische Objekte) im privaten Markt spielen Handwerker eine wichtige Rolle, wo sie mithilfe traditioneller handwerklicher Techniken auf der Grundlage einer **beruflichen Ausbildung** Restaurierungsleistungen erbringen. Akademische und handwerkliche Restaurierung haben jeweils spezielle Anwendungsgebiete und Methoden, ergänzen sich aber vielfach.

Restaurierung eines Freskos von Michelangelo in der Sixtinischen Kapelle (1509): Der Prophet Daniel, vor und nach der zwischen 1980 und 1994^[1] durchgeführten Restaurierung.^[2]

Herkunft

unter Leo X. wurde 1513 das antike Schiffsmodell, das lange vor der Kirche gestanden haben muß und im 15. Jh. bezeugt ist, restauriert und neu aufgestellt; seit 1930 wieder a

Gattung/Funktion/Kulturrep

Inskrift
Bauplastik: Brunnen
zu Monument gehörig: nein
Kulturrepoche: römisch
Gattung: Sonstiges

Datierung

kaiserzeitlich (Chronontology)

Material

Marmor

Erhaltung

fragmentiert
sicher antik ist das Heck bis z
der Antike als Brunnenanlage
bedeckt (durch die moderne f

Bearbeitungen: ergänzt
Moderne Bearbeitungen: die b

Resource Switchboard

Language German

Matching Tools

Group by task

Search for tool

Lookup Tools

- > Open Content Search
- > Open Perseus Scaife Viewer
- > Open Wikipedia DE
- > Open iDAL.gazetteer
- > Open iDAL.vocab DE

View

Berliner Zeitung – Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities

Sie sollte erhalten, mit Sorgfalt gepflegt und nach Möglichkeit originalgetreu restauriert werden.

Vom 21. Januar bis 13. März präsentieren der Maler Matthias Gerlach und der Spielzeugrestaurator Teddy Peter restaurierte Teddys und eigene Kreationen.

Der Speicher wird in Kürze denkmalgerecht restauriert.

1970 wurde das Gebäude restauriert.

Dann beginnt die archäologische Rekonstruktion des Baus, zum Großteil mit den alten, restaurierten Steinen.

Die meisten Bären hat Teddy-Peter völlig heruntergekommen auf dem Flohmarkt entdeckt und in liebevoller Kleinarbeit restauriert.

Warum wird nicht der Palast restauriert, der vielseitig gut verwendbar ist?

Denn die liebevoll restaurierten Häuser hier sind auf besonders wackligem Boden erbaut.

Gemeinsam mit der restaurierten Hauptorgel und deren nunmehr 86 Registern besitzt der Dom nun eine mächtige Orgel-Gesamtanlage mit insgesamt 114 Registern und rund 8700 Pfeifen.

1959 wurde das restaurierte Schloß der Berliner Amtssitz des Bundespräsidenten.

View

German Text Archive (DTA) – Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities

Albrecht Dürer wäre ganz glücklich angekommen, wenn man nicht die unfelige Vorlicht gehabt hätte, feines Papier oben auf zu packen, das denn im Kleide an einigen Stellen gerieben hat, die jetzt restauriert werden.

Über das alles aber hat GOTT dem menlichen noch ein höhers univerfal mitgetheilet / dariñ nicht allein eines elements / fondern aller elementen tugend und quinta essentia machinæ mundi, verborgen liegt / also / daß nichts höhers in der natur dem menlichen leib mag zu gutem erfunden werden / und ist auch dem menlichen leib nichts verwandters oder mehrers weder daffelbig; denn wenn er daffelbig einnimmt / so nimt er ein die quintam essentiam und die gantze regenerierte neue welt / welche die alte zeitförlüche welt / das ist den menchen aus ihres regeneration wieder renovirt / das zerbrochene restauriert, das überflüßige verzehrt / das mangelhafte ergänzt / und den ganzen microcolfum in das recht temperamentum bringt / und darinnen erhält / biß zum bestimmten ziel des todes / der wegen der fünden aufgelezt ist / und nicht allein den

Figure 7: Example: “Restaurierung” in Wikipedia and CLARIN Content Search (note: “restauriert” in the VLO snippet)

As a first step towards a better handling of German words (or any other inflected language), a user can now change the word in the Switchboard pop-up window before it is sent to the linked lookup services. This benefits German-speaking users (who can e.g., change “Samothrace” to the German spelling

“Samothrake”) as well as users with a basic grasp of German (who can e.g. infer the noun “Restaurierung” from the verb form “restauriert”). Figure 7 shows the results for “Restaurierung”.

Experimenting with the list of lookup services in the Switchboard continues. Relevant services and relevant results will be added, and services that turn out to be irrelevant will be removed. Within the Switchboard pop-up window, services should probably be ranked and sorted according to how applicable they are. Also, using a word-form standardisation service for suggesting the standardised word-forms in the Switchboard pop-up window before further lookup or processing would be helpful.

Before the pop-up can be fully integrated in the production version of Arachne, more user testing needs to be done. For example, one user request was for an option to switch the Switchboard pop-up window functionality on and off. There is a need for such an option that is not confusing to the users and at the same time invites users to switch on the Switchboard functionality.

With the integration of Switchboard functionality in Arachne, also issues of control, hosting and software update workflows need to be resolved. With very few exceptions, the iDAI-specific source code for all the iDAI.world services is maintained in GitHub repositories that belong to the DAI. In very rare cases, the code is maintained in repositories that belong to different institutions. While trusted code from other sources is used, e.g., Piwik, Angular as well as many libraries and their dependencies, Arachne contains no Arachne-specific code from non-DAI repositories and the Arachne Frontend does not load any code or content from non-DAI domains. In particular, the JavaScript code for the pop-up must be loaded from a DAI domain. This policy, if continued, may well prove a considerable disadvantage for integrating components from different SSH infrastructures, i.e., the suggested way of solving this is to copy the external service code into the own DAI repository, requiring a duplication of effort for configuration of services. In the discussions with other partners e.g., DARIAH such a reservation was not made explicit. It is recommended that the foreseen continued collaboration between the SSH infrastructures will include statements about (working toward) mutual acceptance of one another's trusted code bases, for instance by code review or quality standards.

E-RIHS use case

E-RIHS establishes itself in the field of Heritage Science and improves its capabilities in the technological and scientific sectors related to Cultural Heritage, integrating state-of-the-art facilities, and offering access to a wide range of high-level scientific tools, as well as to methodologies, data and tools to promote knowledge and innovation in the conservation of Cultural Heritage. As regards the VCR, use cases have been devised that also describe the organization of the infrastructure. Through interdisciplinary access to the four platforms (ARCHLAB²⁷, DIGILAB, FIXLAB²⁸, MOLAB²⁹), E-RIHS supports

²⁷ <https://www.iperionhs.eu/archlab/> (accessed Oct 2021)

²⁸ <https://www.iperionhs.eu/fixlab/> (accessed Oct 2021)

²⁹ <https://www.iperionhs.eu/molab/> (accessed Oct 2021)

a wide variety of research, from smaller object-focussed case studies to large-scale and longer-term collaborative projects. Each form of measurement and result, from the single bit to the spectral image, can be considered as a collection of resources that refer to a type of experiment. The different types of experiments provided by analytical instrumentation and large/medium-scale facilities can equally be considered a collection of possible scientific investigations that can be carried out by the platforms.

It was considered appropriate to develop a practical example from the generic use case that was compiled and entered into the VCR. This experiment concerns the Micro X-ray fluorescence mapping (μ XRF) carried out by the MOLAB platform.

Figure 8: Organisational position of the experiment in relation to the infrastructure and the platform

The use case carried out by E-RIHS concerns a Macro X-Ray Fluorescence analysis on a manuscript of different geographical provenance (1350BC - 19th c.AD), collecting the data obtained from the experiment as a collection. See figure 9.

Figure 9: Example of MA-XRF analysis

The MA-XRF high-resolution distribution images of the chemical elements composing the painting of the manuscripts have provided, in a non-invasive way, the identification of the original materials (pigments) used by the artists and thus increase the knowledge on the artistic, cultural, political, social, technological, and economic aspects in which the miniatures were created. The elemental images also allowed the visualisation of the back of the single pages, no longer readable because over time they have been detached from their main books and glued on cardboard, thus helping their collocation in the original volumes.

This use case is also used to describe the organisation of the E-RIHS distributed research infrastructure, representing the service catalogues made available by the reference laboratories as VCR collections.

CESSDA or shopping-basket use case

The CESSDA use case is particularly interesting and useful with respect to enabling cross-domain use of research data. It is called the shopping-basket or CESSDA use case (CESSDA because it was discussed in detail with CESSDA as a research data scenario that would be the most interesting for that organisation). It is based on an extension of the already existing functionality offered by the combination of CLARIN

VLO³⁰ and the VCR, that allows a user to save the results of a search query performed in the VLO catalogue (figure 10) in the form of a VC for future reference (figure 11). The shopping basket extension is the use of the same VC for storing additional search results from other repositories thus enabling users to collect resources across different repositories.

The screenshot displays the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) search interface. At the top, it shows the VLO logo and navigation links (Search, Contributors, Help). The search results are filtered for 'Afrikaans' and 'song', showing 6 results. The left sidebar contains various filters: Language (Afrikaans selected), Collection, Modality (song selected), Format, Temporal Coverage, Availability, and Search options. The search options section includes a checkbox for 'Only include collection resources' and a button to 'Create virtual collection from search results'. The main content area lists search results with details such as ID, duration, and description. The bottom left corner of the search results area features a button to create a virtual collection.

Figure 10: The CLARIN VLO query for songs in the Afrikaans language. The option to create a virtual collection from the recalled resources is present in the lower left corner.

³⁰ The Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) is CLARIN's central resource catalogue. It offers faceted browsing for resources and a query interface. <https://vlo.clarin.eu/>

The rationale for this use case is that integration of the VCR in SSH repositories will make it easier to gather and reuse resources from all over the SSH domain.

Virtual Collection Registry Browse **Create** My Collections Help

daan.broeder_di.huc.knaw.nl@clarin.eu CLARIN

Create / Edit Collection: Advanced Mode

Name: VLO search results

Description: New collection description

Note: Markdown supported (cheat sheet)

Keywords: code:afr, song

Authors: anonymous,

Family Name: New author family name

Given Name: New author given name

Email: New author email

Affiliation: New author affiliation (optional)
Press <enter> to add this author

References:

Add new reference by URL or PID

Set a title for this new reference
Press <enter> to add this reference

NE080915-04_C (hdl:2196/00-0000-0000-000D-AB23-C@format=cmdi) ✖
 Afrikaans version of a song that was translated by E from Afrikaans to Nluu. Nluu version: NE080915-03_A

NE080825-03_E (hdl:2196/00-0000-0000-000D-AA22-A@format=cmdi) ✖
 Duration: 56 seconds (Nluu with Afrikaans comments)
 A lullaby which E remembers and which her mother (Nlangkusi) had sung to her.

Save Collection Cancel

Figure 11: Virtual collection of Afrikaans songs in the Virtual Collection Registry

In the SSHOC project a test and demonstration scenario is planned by offering the shopping-basket use case to be applied from different SSH repositories and catalogues. Next to the integration of the VCR with the CLARIN VLO, the VCR integration in the ARCHE repository³¹ (DARIAH) there is an integration planned

³¹ The resource catalogue of the ACDH, <https://arche.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/browser/discover/root> (accessed Oct 2021)

in Q3 2021 of the VCR in the SND repository catalogue³² (CESSDA) which together would demonstrate coverage over the broad SSH. Currently also discussions with SSHOC task 5.2 “Hosting and sharing data repositories” are underway concerning integration of the VCR in the SSHOC Dataverse repository software.

General use cases and vision for SSH interoperability

Next to the above use cases, that emerged from discussion and expressed preferences of the SSHOC partners, also a number of general use cases were identified for the Switchboard and the VCR. This general context was a recurring topic during the whole SSHOC project period and although not all ideas could have been implemented within SSHOC, the established working relations could materialise in the future in other contexts.

VC resources consolidation and download (in combination with CMDIexplorer tool)

In the reporting period, the CMDIExplorer was implemented, a tool that visualizes collections described with CMDI metadata (according to ISO 24622-1 and 24622-2). Users of CMDIExplorer³³ have multiple ways to supply such CMDI files to the software: they can upload a CMDI file from their file system or specify a URL/handle that points to a CMDI file, or even copy and paste the contents of a CMDI file into a text area. In the future, CMDIExplorer will also be callable from the Virtual Collection Registry (directly, or via the Switchboard) whose collections are automatically described with CMDI. In each case, CMDIExplorer visualizes a collection as a hierarchical tree. It makes each part of the collection (tree) actionable, for instance, each resource is downloadable, or it can be sent to the Switchboard for further processing. With CMDIExplorer, users can hence select the tree’s root and download the entire collection at once. In the future, users will be able to send an entire collection, or parts thereof, to WebLicht-Batch, see below.

Batch processing of VCs/ integration of VC in Weblicht workflows

The Virtual Collection Registry allows users to build and make available collections of resources. Often, but not always, these collections are *homogeneous*, that is, they contain resources of the same data-type, say *text/plain*. However, when users want to process the collection, say for an automatic linguistic analysis, they must *manually* break-up the collection into its individual resources, and then process each resource one by one.

CMDIExplorer helps users to visualise and navigate through potentially complex collections. In a hierarchical tree, they can select a leaf node (that is, a single resource), and send it via the Switchboard to an NLP tool of their choice. More importantly, however, they can easily build a homogeneous sub-

³² The Swedish National Data Service (SND) is the Swedish CESSDA node, and operates a metadata catalogue for Social Sciences and other disciplines, <https://snd.gu.se/en/catalogue/search> (accessed Oct 2021)

³³ CMDI Explorer: <https://weblicht.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/CMDIExplorer> (accessed Oct 2021)

collection of, say, plain text files, and download it as a zip file for further processing, with for example WebLicht-Batch, see below.

In the SSHOC community, there is a good demand to better support and further automate the processing of collections. For this, WebLicht-Batch, an initial prototype for the batch-processing of collections is being implemented³⁴. WebLicht-Batch helps users to feed multiple files, one-by-one into the WebLicht workflow engine. At the time of writing, users can use WebLicht-Batch to upload a zip file containing a *homogeneous* (and flat) collection of files, select one of WebLicht's predefined workflows (EasyChains), or upload their own chain file, and start the processing. WebLicht-Batch then interacts with WebLicht's chainer back-end to process each file of the collection with the chosen workflow, and subsequently creates a zip file with the processing results (a set of files in TCF format³⁵).

Key-value pair type metadata profiles for Virtual Collections

The work on enabling the automatic processing of virtual collections did show a need to improve the virtual collection metadata in such a way that the metadata of the virtual collection's constituent resources can reflect the intentions of the VC creator. E.g., if a researcher creates a VC for investigating the efficiency of different OCR workflows, the metadata and data-type of the VC's constituents (JPEG, TIFF) cannot reflect the OCR intent. Better and more appropriate options for processing become available if the VC metadata can express that intent. A maximum of flexibility providing for potentially many different processing tools and frameworks can be provided by augmenting the current VC metadata schema with a set of free form key-value pairs. Specific profiles of such key/value pairs could then be an agreed requirement for interoperability of VCs with the processing tool or framework. How to specify and negotiate which profiles are available in the collection or required for the workflow is still open for discussion. Within SSHOC an implementation for the WebLicht predefined workflows will be investigated and addressed.

Presentation of services and direct engagement with researchers

Activities to engage researchers were pursued along two lines: (1) Communication with disseminators or representatives of research domains. (2) Direct communication was (or will be) conducted by workshops or public consultations. Such an engagement is planned before the end of 2021 in cooperation with LIBER with the aim to learn more about the requirements of researchers who are not familiar yet with services like Switchboard or Virtual Collection Registry.

Although the discussion about the usability of Switchboard and VCR for the different SSHOC stakeholder was planned and executed mainly by contact with the managers of the infrastructures, the benefits of contact with researchers has become clear, if only to be able to communicate in broadly understandable

³⁴ Prototype of WebLicht Batch: <https://weblight.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/weblight-batch/> (accessed Oct 2021)

³⁵ https://weblight.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/weblightwiki/index.php/The_TCF_Format (accessed Oct 2021)

terms about the tools and application scenarios beyond the immediate CLARIN domain. One good result in this respect is the publication of SSHOC factsheets for both the Switchboard³⁶ and the VCR³⁷ which have been created together with LIBER and aim at visibility for the services in the European Open Science Cloud.

An important role with regard to addressing disseminators in research infrastructures played the project internal presentations at the SSHOC consortium meetings. As a reminder, the SSHOC project consists of 20 partner organisations and 27 associate organisations, thus ensuring a good access to many SSH communities in the European Research Area. For example, the Switchboard was demonstrated at the SSHOC consortium meeting March 23rd and 24th, 2021, and a demonstration of the VCR with the shopping-basket use-case was provided at the consortium meeting October 5th and 6th, 2021.

At the SSHOC consortium meeting on March 23/24, 2021, Wolfgang Schmidle from the DAI partner demonstrated the use of the Switchboard integrated in the DAI catalogue for accessing selected terms in different dictionaries and information systems³⁸. And at the October 5/6 2021 consortium meeting Willem Elbers presented the use of the VCR for collecting the results of search queries in different repositories. These presentations were meant both to give an example of the WP3 activities as well as solicit interest in the tools themselves.

Apart from these project-aimed presentations the topics have been highlighted in several other presentations or talks, such as of CLARIAH-DE at the FORGE21³⁹, a DARIAH-DE Working Paper dedicated to the integration of CLARIN and DARIAH resources⁴⁰, or a lecture by CLARIAH-DE colleagues on integration scenarios at DANS⁴¹.

³⁶ Elisa Gorgaini. (2021). Language Resource Switchboard - SSHOC Service Catalogue's Factsheets Series (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5495696>

³⁷ Elisa Gorgaini. (2021). Virtual Collection Registry - SSHOC Service Catalogue's Factsheets Series (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5482899>

³⁸ Available as project internal documentation.

³⁹ Helfer, Felix, Jegan, Robin, Buddenbohm, Stefan, Eckart, Thomas, & Gradl, Tobias. (2021, September 3). Generische und fachspezifische Integration in der Forschungsinfrastruktur CLARIAH-DE. FORGE 2021: Forschungsdaten in den Geisteswissenschaften - Mapping the Landscape - Geisteswissenschaftliches Forschungsdatenmanagement zwischen lokalen und globalen, generischen und spezifischen Lösungen (FORGE2021), Cologne. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5379641>

⁴⁰ Thomas Eckart, Tobias Gradl, Robin Jegan, Eliza Margaretha, Antonina Werthmann, Felix Helfer, Stefan Buddenbohm. "CLARIAH-DE Cross-Service Search: Prospects and Benefits of Merging Subject-specific Services". DARIAH-DE Working Papers Nr. 41. Göttingen: DARIAH-DE, 2021. URN: <urn:nbn:de:gbv:7-dariah-2021-1-9>

⁴¹ Buddenbohm, Stefan, & Eckart, Thomas. (2021, March 23). Merging Subject-Specific Searches of CLARIN and DARIAH in CLARIAH-DE: Challenges of Technical Integration. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4628889>

Collaboration with other SSHOC tasks and other projects

The SSH Open Marketplace

The SSH Open Marketplace (Marketplace) is being created in SSHOC WP7 “Creating the SSH Open Marketplace”. It is a discovery portal which pools and contextualises resources for Social Sciences and Humanities research communities: tools, services, training materials, datasets and workflows. The service highlights and showcases solutions and research practices for every step of the SSH research data life cycle.

The discussion in task 3.6 and together with WP7 about the potential use of Switchboard and VCR in the Marketplace culminated in the documentation of six use cases⁴² of possible connections between the SSH Open Marketplace either to the Switchboard or to the Virtual Collection Registry. The information below reflects the implementation status in autumn 2021:

- Creation of a virtual collection with records from the marketplace: Partly possible/implemented. A crucial point remains with the persistence of the marketplace records which is at the current state of the service not guaranteed.
- Inclusion of the VCR as a feature in the marketplace: Suspended/not implemented. Currently a direct integration of this shopping basket function in the marketplace is not planned due to the priority of other development work. However, this may be a promising feature on a future roadmap of the marketplace.
- Invocation of the Switchboard from the marketplace based on MIME type. Suspended/not implemented. This use case is hampered by the composition of records in the marketplace. The marketplace contains a broad range of content types, e.g., training material, data sets, software, services, or documentation material. Only for content types with a MIME type the use case is reasonable as the look-up function of the Switchboard relies on the MIME type of the presented

⁴² Buddenbohm, Stefan, Broeder, Daan, Eisner, Marthe Irene, Illmayer, Klaus, & Durco, Matej. (2020). Collaborative Use Cases between SSH Open Marketplace and the Language Resource Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4442320> Please consult this document and its addendum for details on the scenarios including the Marketplace and be aware, that for this document only a summary of these results had been written.

file. This use case would fit perfectly for a research data repository and only to a lesser degree to the marketplace⁴³.

- Invocation/Call up of MP from Switchboard with a search string: Implemented. A call-up of the MP from the Switchboard is under preparation. Taking the contextualisation of the MP records into account, this use case is straight forward. A user coming from the Switchboard lands, for instance, on the detail page for the tool he or she initially looked up at the Switchboard. The MP in turn shows related or similar tools and the user may inquire about them.
- Switchboard as ingested source in the MP: Implemented. The Switchboard's tool inventory is already included as an information source in the MP. However, a possible improvement option remains to enhance the tool descriptions on the side of the Switchboard. As the Switchboard is an authoritative source for the MP, any enhancements (better illustrations, more description) would become visible in the MP.
- MP desktop tool info for the Switchboard: Solved. The Switchboard's tool inventory includes desktop tools. For this reason, a dedicated implementation of this use case is not necessary anymore.

Collaboration with SSHOC Task 5.2

The main goal of the Task 5.2 “Hosting and Sharing of Data Repositories” is to design and develop a service on the EOSC cloud platform, which will provide SSH institutions without a data repository service, such a facility for their designated communities. The service is built upon the Dataverse platform⁴⁴. Dataverse is an open-source software platform, developed and maintained by the Harvard Institute for Quantitative Social Science (IQSS) since 2006. It has a modular design principle using APIs, that allow for distributed file storage, and supports the building of further micro-services on top.

⁴³ See the Switchboard integrations mentioned in the DARIAH-DE and ARCHE use cases, which link research data repositories to the Switchboard.

⁴⁴ Dataverse website: <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/> (accessed Oct 2021)

Figure 12: Integration of the Switchboard in a Dataverse platform

The goal of the collaboration with this task has been to build a software component to integrate a Dataverse platform with the Switchboard. The Switchboard can be seen as a Virtual Tool Registry: for a given resource, it identifies all tools that can process the resource, sorts the tools in terms of the tasks they perform, and presents a task-oriented list to the user.

Figure 13: Dataverse Switchboard integration showing available lookup services in the pop-up window

Users can then select and invoke the tool of their choosing, all relevant information about the resource is passed onto the tool automatically by the LRS.

In this activity, an integration between the LRS and a Dataverse platform has been implemented at two levels:

- Data object level: a user that browses the Dataverse repositories, can select a specific file in a dataverse and invoke the Switchboard from the Dataverse UI. The screenshot in figure 12 shows an example of this integration: in the Dataverse UI for datasets the 'Explore' icon shown on the right of a file name opens a dropdown menu, when the "Process type file with LRS" option is selected, the file is automatically uploaded to the LRS, along with the mime type information, and the Resource Switchboard User Interface (UI) is opened on a new web page.
- Application viewer level: in Dataverse it is possible to preview text and pdf files by invoking specific viewers, the integration component enables a user to invoke text processing and dictionary lookup functionality offered by services integrated in the Switchboard from the UI of the viewer. The screenshot in figure 13 shows an example of this functionality: when a user selects a text fragment in the Dataverse previewer, the Switchboard pop-up⁴⁵ menu is displayed. If the selection consists of up to 3 words, the tools presented to the user are dictionaries, gazetteers, encyclopedias and other reference tools that could provide information on the selected words.

The software component, called `dataverse-lrs`, has been built following the technical guidelines defined for integrating external tools in the Dataverse platform⁴⁶, it consists of a set of 'add-on' modules that can be installed on an instance of the Dataverse platform to add the Switchboard integration functionalities. The installation guide, the technical documentation, and the source code of the `dataverse-lrs` component are available on the GitHub SSHOC-Dataverse repository⁴⁷. Currently also discussions are underway about integration between VCR and the SSHOC Dataverse repository software.

National level infrastructure support - the CLARIAH projects and the German NFDI

A recent development on the national level revolves around the emergence of CLARIAH-DE, CLARIAH-NL, and CLARIAH-AT⁴⁸ (as of 2021), which are initiatives to combine CLARIN and DARIAH in those countries. The common denominator of the CLARIAH projects is that they address humanities- and language-related study topics beyond the humanities.

⁴⁵ Basically the same function as implemented in the DAI's Arachne use-case.

⁴⁶ Dataverse: <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/admin/external-tools.html> (accessed Oct 2021)

⁴⁷ GitHub repository for the Dataverse switchboard integration: <https://github.com/SSHOC/dataverse-lrs>

⁴⁸ Although no active communication with CLARIAH-AT had been maintained in SSHOC.

For instance, SSHOC T3.6 maintained several discussion threads with the German CLARIAH-DE⁴⁹ research infrastructure, which is addressing the (formerly separate) user bases of CLARIN-D and DARIAH-DE. CLARIAH-DE is the merger of CLARIN-D and DARIAH-DE and of interest for SSHOC especially from the perspective of infrastructure integration and interlinking of services⁵⁰. Through CLARIAH-DE, SSHOC is able to take part in discussions in the national research infrastructure landscape. The same holds true for CLARIAH-NL.

Together with CLARIN ERIC and DARIAH-DE T3.6 analysed integration scenarios for all German services and implemented those feasible from the DARIAH-DE service portfolio⁵¹:

- DARIAH-DE-owned repositories such as the TextGrid repository and the DARIAH-DE repository were registered as CLARIN data centres. This enhances the accessible research data through CLARIN-owned search services such as the VLO or FCS.
- The Switchboard now includes/links to DARIAH-DE owned services: the GeoBrowser, DKPro-Wrapper, TextGrid Laboratory, TopicsExplorer. The Switchboard suggests these services according to a matching MIME type.
- The TextGrid repository and the DARIAH-DE repository allow now for a call-up of the Switchboard. A user may “send” a selected data set to the Switchboard and receive service suggestions.
- The DARIAH-DE Data Federation Architecture (DFA) is now linked with the FCS, respectively the DARIAH-DE Generic Search is now connected to the CLARIN FCS. This improves the user experiences for users of both services.

Apart from these results, there were also discussion threads that either led to no results or remain open at the closing of the SSHOC report, partly reaching back to a joint workshop of CLARIAH-DE and SSHOC that took place in Göttingen in December 2019. Several scenarios have been discussed. Those which led to results have been described, several others have been terminated without result.

A similar consultation had been maintained with CLARIAH-NL. The Dutch CLARIAH project⁵² made it mandatory for its NLP services to be registered with the Switchboard. This project not only aims to facilitate easy access from users, but also as an explicit registration of an NLP service that can be easily tested. There is a strong need for having reliable, testable registration of services. The registration with the Switchboard, is first checked by domain experts on stability and usability and has the advantage of making the service explicit and testable. Next to the EOSC portal onboarding process for general services

⁴⁹ Buddenbohm, Stefan, Friedrichs, Sonja, & Walker, Nathalie. (2020). CLARIAH-DE - Added value of the infrastructure merger. Scholarly Primitives - DARIAH Annual Event 2020, Zagreb, Croatia. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4247243>

⁵⁰ And appears also as DARIAH-DE use case in this report.

⁵¹ <https://de.dariah.eu/en/dienste-und-werkzeuge>

⁵² CLARIAH website: <https://www.clariah.nl> (accessed Oct 2021)

being promoted by EOSC, a curated thematic service registry such as the Switchboard that allows direct easy access to the registered services can be more effective empowering end-users.

SSHOC is the social science and humanities contribution to the European Open Science Cloud but relies to a large part for its results on the work and existing resources of its national partners, which usually have been active for some years in their respective areas of interest. These national partners form an important link between the European and national level of research infrastructures. Often these national partners come with a seasoned experience in the development, provision, and shared ownership of research resources (often already addressing a European user community) and are able to exert substantial resources due to national funding schemes.

The German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) - as a prominent example of a national research infra project in the context of SSHOC - is currently taking shape and will be a formative framework for research infrastructure providers in the next few years with an annual funding budget of up to 90 million EUR per year until 2028 over all disciplines. The NFDI is organised - to a large part - along infrastructure consortia, usually covering disciplines.

With the NFDI, several implications for SSHOC can be seen. Implications may be directly related to specific research infrastructures SSHOC maintains relations with, such as CLARIAH-DE, but considering some basic services such as PID, AAI, LTP, also for other parties. In the long run, the groups of the humanities consortia mentioned may become an important partner for European initiatives like SSHOC.

The expectations from a project like SSHOC towards such national frameworks are:

- Reliable partnerships for sustaining matured research resources, e.g., an innovative service developed within a European project and addressing similar user bases could be owned by a national partner. This becomes increasingly important in view of the considerable resources for infrastructure provided via national funders.
- Pooling of resources and competencies for joint goals, e.g., like practiced with the improved integration of CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH, and E-RIHS resources during SSHOC.
- Joint development of standards and best practices apart from involvement in existing initiatives like RDA.

Status of the Switchboard and VCR services development and operations

The software development of Switchboard and VCR was planned in MS12 and VCR summary document as well as possible. Much depended also on the discussions with SSHOC stakeholders about Switchboard and VCR use cases that took place in parallel with the development work, and the planning in MS12 was updated regularly. Some changes occurred with respect to the original planning of task 3.6.

Originally it was planned that the T3.6 UGOE partner would contribute to the further development of the VCR by implementing an API that was developed in the context of the RDA repository WG. Unfortunately, due to lack of software developer resources, this plan had to be abandoned and in consultation with the project coordinator were able to move resources to the T3.6 EKUT partner for other development work.

This work is reported as far as possible in the section of this document titled [General use cases and vision for SSH interoperability](#): VC resources consolidation and download (in combination with the CMDIexplorer tool) and batch-processing of VCs/ integration of VC in WebLicht workflows. The two following sections will give detailed information about the software development and operations of the Switchboard and VCR services.

Switchboard

The Switchboard is managed as an open-source project hosted on several different GitHub repositories: one repository for the source code⁵³, another repository for the tool specifications⁵⁴ and a third repository for technical documentation⁵⁵. The Switchboard web application is available at different sites or instances: the main one is the production instance⁵⁶, where only stable versions and tools are deployed. A beta testing instance⁵⁷ is used for deploying code changes that require additional testing. A third development instance⁵⁸ is used for demonstration of new features and new service integrations and is the most up to date. This instance is also referred to as the SSHOC version from this and other documents.

An important aspect of the Switchboard functionality are the integrated services that are available in the picklist for a user to select and process a resource. Each of these services is specified in a configuration

⁵³ Github repository of the Switchboard: <https://github.com/clarin-eric/switchboard>

⁵⁴ Github repository of the Switchboard tool inventory: <https://github.com/clarin-eric/switchboard-tool-registry>

⁵⁵ Switchboard documentation: <https://github.com/clarin-eric/switchboard-doc>

⁵⁶ Production instance of the Switchboard: switchboard.clarin.eu

⁵⁷ Beta instance of the Switchboard: <http://beta-switchboard.clarin.eu/>

⁵⁸ Development instance of the Switchboard: <https://switchboard.clarin-dev.eu/>

file whose format is open and clearly described in the technical documentation. Tool creators are welcome to require the addition of their tool to the Switchboard; this process is clearly documented⁵⁹ and consists in creating a configuration file with the tool's metadata in the GitHub tools repository. The new service will automatically become visible in the testing instance and will be evaluated in terms of stability and usefulness before being also made available in the production Switchboard instance.

In the last three years the Switchboard project has released four new major versions and many more minor stable versions and testing or release candidates. In this rapid development phase, the following important features were added:

1. Integration of the profiler, which is a module able to automatically detect the common file data formats and especially able to detect the file data formats used in the NLP domain. This allowed automatic recognition of TEI, FoLiA and TCF formats and consequently a better user experience when working with these files (see Appendix A, item SRB1).
2. Addition of the "pop-up" mode, a small pop-up version of the Switchboard which can be easily integrated into a repository web site (e.g., for the DAI and Dataverse use-cases). This feature was made possible by the creation of a new version of the invocation API. The pop-up allows the users to quickly inspect repository files and test their utility and is successfully used by the VLO (see Appendix A, items SD0 and SD1).
3. Addition of a "lookup mode", made possible by the Switchboard pop-up, which enables users to quickly lookup words (or word compounds) in general or specialized reference sites, dictionaries, thesauruses, or marketplaces (see Appendix A, item SI3).
4. Update of the tool specification format to a new version, which allowed the addition of new fields (e.g., keywords or resource limitations for some tools) and the addition of new tool classes (locally installable tools, in contrast to web-only accessible tools). Both the previous tool format and the new one was formalized via JSON schemas.
5. Support for a varied combination of tool input parameters: multiple inputs, variadic inputs (that match multiple resources) and optional inputs. This feature was necessary for a better integration with specific tools (see Appendix A, item SI1) and is currently only enabled in the development instance.
6. Support for content inspection in the case of text data files and support for inspection of data files packed into archives (zip and tar formats). Individual data files in archives can also be selected and treated as separate input resources. Support for unpacking compressed files (bz2, gz) has also been added (see Appendix A, items SD3 and SD4).
7. Text extraction from files of specific types (e.g., PDF, Word, HTML), increasing the range of tools that match such files (see Appendix A, item SD5).

⁵⁹ Documentation how to add tools to the Switchboard:

<https://github.com/clarin-eric/switchboard-tool-registry#how-to-add-a-tool-to-the-switchboard> (accessed Oct 2021)

8. Multiple UI improvements: a completely revamped UI with a new tool list design, Markdown support in the tools specifications for better tool descriptions, the use of badges to indicate access restricted tools or other categories.

In this period many new tools have been fully integrated with the Switchboard, most of them from the NLP domain. Some integrated tools outside of this domain are the following:

- Ariadne Visual Media service, a visualizer of 3D model files (used in digital archaeology)
- CMDI Explorer, a browser of resources linked from CMDI collection files
- GeoBrowser, a visualizer of geographic data.

The BAS ASR, WebMAUS⁶⁰ and WebMINNI services were partly integrated, with the tools being recommended to the user in case of an input match but without an automated transfer of data. The EXMARaLDA, TextGridLab, DKPro-Wrapper and TopicsExplorer tools were added as standalone tools, being recommended for local installation in case of a match.

The TextGrid⁶¹, DARIAH-DE, ARCHE and DAI repositories were integrated with the Switchboard. The CMDIExplorer web application, although not a repository, added support to send data files from CMDI collections to the Switchboard.

VCR

The Virtual Collection Registry (VCR) service, operated by CLARIN ERIC, currently consist of three instances: (1) the main production instance⁶², (2) the beta or staging instance⁶³ which can be used by third party data catalogues to test integration with the submission endpoint and (3) the development instance⁶⁴ which is used to deploy and test new and possibly unstable features.

Source code and issues are hosted on GitHub⁶⁵. External contributors are encouraged to fork to a new repository and create pull requests to include contributions in the main repository. Issues can be created and commented on by anyone. This workflow did not require any changes to support the SSHOC project. The instances are managed on GitLab.com, packaged as publicly accessible docker images⁶⁶ and

⁶⁰ Florian Schiel (2015). A Statistical Model for Predicting Pronunciation. In: Proc. of the ICPhS 2015, Glasgow, UK, paper 195

⁶¹ Neuroth, Heike/ Rapp, Andrea/ Söring, Sibylle (2015): TextGrid: Von der Community – für die Community. Eine Virtuelle Forschungsumgebung für die Geisteswissenschaften. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3249/webdoc-3947>

⁶² Production instance of the VCR: <https://collections.clarin.eu>

⁶³ Beta instance of the VCR: <https://beta-collections.clarin.eu>

⁶⁴ Development instance of the VCR: <https://alpha-collections.clarin.eu>

⁶⁵ Github repository for the VCR: <https://github.com/clarin-eric/VirtualCollectionRegistry>

⁶⁶ Docker images of the VCR: <https://gitlab.com/CLARIN-ERIC/docker-alpine-supervisor-java-tomcat-vcr>

deployed via docker-compose. The docker-compose projects can contain secrets and host specific details and therefore are not publicly accessible.

Based on the discussions with various communities a number of use cases have been defined as described in [Community use case discussions](#). These use case have resulted in a set of feature requests for the VCR, organized in three milestones⁶⁷. When completed, these features should be enough to realise the use cases as described with the communities.

Milestone 1.6.x, in production

Many small incremental improvements and bug fixes have been included in this release. Focussing on the SSHOC related improvements discussions on the submission endpoint were started. This is the endpoint used by external data catalogues to submit collection data based on search results. The new features include support to merge the resources of a submission into an existing collection. The endpoint has also been extended to store a search query and the referrer hostname with submitted resources. This information is also visualized in the collection details page and can be used to filter on collections.

Workspace integration, as mentioned in the description of work, is supported via a manual workflow. A collection identifier can be supplied to the CMDI explorer⁶⁸. The CMDI explorer allows downloading the (public) resources of a collection as a zip archive. By downloading this archive to a local folder which is synced to a workspace (nextcloud, dropbox, google drive, ...) the workspace integration is completed.

Other new features include support to generate API tokens from the user profile page and use these tokens to authenticate with the REST API. This enables cli based and automated interaction with the API. The API has also been documented based on the OpenAPI initiative⁶⁹ specification. When publishing a collection a DOI, allowing better citation, is minted as well.

Milestone 1.7.x, under development

For this milestone forking (deployed on the development instance) and versioning (currently under development) is planned. If a user forks a collection, the collection is copied into a new collection and the user will become the owner of this collection. A reference to the original collection is stored and on publication a new persistent identifier is assigned. If a published collection is edited, a new version is created. The new version is assigned a new PID on publication and a PID is minted or updated to always point to the most recent published version of the collection. This allows a user to cite and share the PID pointing to a specific version, which should remain stable over time, of a collection or to cite and share the PID pointing to the latest version, which can change over time when updates are made, of the

⁶⁷ The three VCR milestones: <https://github.com/clarin-eric/VirtualCollectionRegistry/milestones>

⁶⁸ CMDI Explorer: <https://weblicht.sfs.uni-tuebingen.de/CMDIExplorer/>

⁶⁹ OPENAPI Initiative: <https://openapis.org> (accessed Oct 2021)

collection. The collection details page should also show links to the other and latest versions of the collection.

Milestone 1.8.x, planned

Based on the use-cases it is clear that collaborative editing functionality is considered important. For a first version of collaborative editing a system based on link sharing is considered. A user can share a link with a set of co-editors. Anyone with the link can make changes to the collection. To avoid issues with conflicts a locking solution is considered which comes with obvious drawbacks or alternatively a 'suggesting' solution. With this approach, other editors' changes are saved as suggestions which must be accepted or rejected by the owner of the collection.

Sustainability aspects

Both Switchboard and VCR are services created and operated by CLARIN ERIC and CLARIN partners intended for the CLARIN domain, and although these services have been onboarded in the EOSC, no demand was placed on them from outside the CLARIN domain, and both maintenance and operational responsibility remained uniquely with CLARIN.

SSHOC task3.6 has been investigating extending both tools for the benefit of the SSH and additionally investigating how to organise aspects of governance and maintenance and operational responsibility. This could not happen without also looking at how SSHOC in general considers such challenges. Such as there are the other services developed in the project that need to be made sustainable also after the SSHOC project e.g., the SSH Open Marketplace from WP7 and the ConversionHub from SSHOC task 3.5.

In the past, collaboration projects such as DASISH maintained as a default solution that the partner managing the task responsible for the service creation committed itself also for maintaining (at least for some years) to the maintenance and operations of the service. This can still be a sensible solution especially if the service scope is closely in line with that partner's mission.

At the start of the SSHOC project the unfolding of EOSC institutions and projects was still largely in preparation. The only agreed fixed feature for obtaining visibility and later perhaps sustainable funding for services was the onboarding of services in the EOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace⁷⁰. Currently, the lack of clear EOSC business and funding models makes the planning of the exploitation and sustainability of the services developed by the project a very difficult task.

Task 3.6 started with the motivation of advancing and generalising the two data management tools CLARIN Switchboard and VCR, looking for synergies with other activities in SSHOC and actively developing for use cases beyond the CLARIN origin. When developing the use cases and resulting requirements, the

⁷⁰ EOSC Portal Marketplace: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu> (accessed Oct 2021)

possibility was left open that there was a need for developing and/or operating special versions of the Switchboard or VCR, separately from the production versions currently being maintained and operated by CLARIN, although such a solution would not be optimal from a perspective of efficiency. For instance, CLARIN has a strict policy regarding accepting new registrations of services in the CLARIN Switchboard based on service stability and usefulness of such services for the CLARIN community. For the purpose of experimenting with useful service integrations for the humanities, a more flexible policy is required. Operating two different versions of what are largely the same services, does have problematic consequences. Aspects of providing correct documentation, name branding, EOSC onboarding will be much more complex. On top of which comes the governance and sustainability problem for services that do not clearly fall within the scope of one single partner.

Although within SSHOC, the work regarding governance and sustainability of shared services is ongoing, since suitable solutions must be found for shared services like the SSH Open Marketplace, such solutions are currently not clear yet. However, if partners are willing to co-design and operate a useful separate version for a different community, this should always be possible. All the software involved is available as open source and between the partners involved sufficient good-will and collaboration exist – also via other projects and initiatives, e.g., CLARIAH-DE.

A different reason why a separate version could be useful, is the aspect of IT resources. In a situation where a large majority of users of the Switchboard or VCR are from outside the CLARIN domain, it would be desirable to have a common service sustainability and operations agreement that provides for sharing costs, or else have a separate instance operated by an organisation related to most users. Such problems and considerations are debated often in the context of planning common research infrastructure for different communities with each their own separate funding channels.

In the case of the SSH domain and the Switchboard and VCR services, the resources necessary to operate these services are not likely to be a problem. The limiting factors will rather be human resources necessary for software maintenance and further development. In this context after analysing the requirements from the SSHOC-inspired use cases and considering also the general service improvements for CLARIN Switchboard and VCR from CLARIN's own needs, it appeared that:

- For the VCR service no separate version is needed. All suggested changes for the VCR are considered useful for the CLARIN community and fit in the long-term development plans. CLARIN also will support use from other communities beyond its own as long as the usage remains according to guidelines⁷¹ and within expectations of fair use.
- In the case of the Switchboard the situation is different. As described above the CLARIN policy is directed towards accepting only stable, tested and (for the CLARIN audience) useful services as part of the set of integrated Switchboard services. For the Humanities and especially in the

⁷¹ The VCR is intended to create stable references to data collections that are meant to persist, not transient products.

SSHOC context a more liberal policy was required. For this purpose, a special SSHOC version was operated by EKUT (see [Switchboard Development](#) section).

Currently the CLARIN VCR is operated by CLARIN ERIC and hosted by the IDS (German CLARIN centre). CLARIN ERIC plans to keep operating a stable version that may also be useful for other domains. Other versions supporting new (experimental) functionality can be operated by others. In the discussions with CESSDA it was pointed out that there should be clear solutions and guarantees with regards to operations of the SSHOC VCR before CESSDA can commit using it⁷².

Note that also for the Switchboard from an efficiency perspective it is preferable not to operate different instances. But if needed this would be possible, especially since the difference between the two instances would be a configuration and management issue (managing and configuring different sets of Switchboard integrated services) rather than different software branches.

Plans for the future

In principle both services are of use to the broader research community, and although its operation and maintenance is, with the predominant use within the CLARIN domain, now better placed within the SSH/CLARIN domain, it should be integrated with and provided through EOSC channels. Especially a general tool as the VCR is a candidate for being (co-)operated by an EOSC infrastructure provider as a core EOSC component.

In general, the issue of sustainability through EOSC is closely related to the scope and potential uptake of such services. Both the VCR and Switchboard, already stable and mature services currently still lack the uptake it deserves. An explanation for this can be found when looking at the ownership of these resources. A similar situation can be found, for instance, when looking at services of other ERICs, for instance the DARIAH-DE Repository. The limited disciplinary scope and ownership of such services are on the one hand advantageous for the sustainability and product maintenance because they usually are integral parts of broader infrastructure portfolios.

It should be in the interest of any research infrastructure to explore further usage potentials of its offerings. Of course, the disciplinary scope is a limiting factor, but interoperability or cross-domain collaboration could be pursued in future projects inspired by SSHOC. SSHOC as the social sciences and humanities contribution to the EOSC proved useful in this regard. The project, and particularly WP3, was a fruitful discussion arena for the SSH ERICs to explore linkages, service integrations and exploiting other research and data domains.

⁷² This has now been cleared with CLARIN ERIC and a commitment was provided that within limits of reason CLARIN ERIC will operate a VCR meeting the requirements of current SSHOC use cases.

Within SSHOC through various means a continued awareness of both services is ensured, most prominently the Key Exploitable Results documentation⁷³ has to be mentioned here. This will contribute to awareness within the EOSC context, which should be a formative player for research infrastructures in the next few years. Next to that, awareness is created with key SSH infrastructure operators and builders, and there are good opportunities for co-design in a SSH Open Cluster collaboration context.

Likely the most important cornerstone of the services' sustainability and continued development will be the ERICs, primary CLARIN. But as mentioned in several chapters of this report the other ERICs will also have a part in this. On the national level there are potential actors: the German NFDI initiative, connected to CLARIAH-DE, the Dutch CLARIAH project and other national infrastructure projects will likely provide additional opportunities to address SSH researchers.

⁷³ SSHOC Key Exploitable Results are available as project internal documentation.

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Appendix. Status of Switchboard and VCR development items related to SSHOC

	Name extension	Responsible	Estimated time/date	Comment	Status Sept 2020 - Q7	Status Feb2021 - Q9	Status Sept 2021
SD0	Develop next version Switchboard API, allowing easy upgrades of the Switchboard UI	EKUT	Q5 (Jan-Mar 2020), 1PM	Related to SD1,2,3,5	done		done
SD1	Lightweight Switchboard pop-up Including usage examples e.g., dictionaries Investigate the JS library vs Browser plugin approach	EKUT	Q6 (Apr-Jun 2020), 2PM	considered plug-in approach not viable.	partially done, DAI dictionary implemented in dev version, guidelines how-to implement are available	pop-up window [MD1] refined, not integrated in any repository, test-page available, to be implemented in CLARIN version, integration in ARACHNE still under discussion	done
SD2	Support for Data Dowsing, rule-based extraction of data references from metadata/landing pages	EKUT, CNR	Q7 (Jun-Sept 2020), 1PM	Test repositories to still be identified	Delayed	Postponed until CLARIN Digital Object Gateway [MD2] plans clarified	postponed
SD3	(Interactive) content visualization depending on data-type	EKUT, OEAW	Q7 (Jun-Sept 2020), 1PM	Needed for SD4, SD6	Delayed	Q10 together with iteration over container content, see also SEP11	done for text-type and container-type
SD4	Supporting (data) containers e.g. zip, tar	CLARIN/EKUT	Q7 (Jun-Sept 2020), 1PM	Where possible use external services	Delayed	Q10	done
SD5	Supporting data conversion	EKUT, CNR	Q8 (Oct-Dec 2020), 1PM	with T3.5 (FSD) discuss with 3.5, call existing conversion without UI services through Weblicht		analyse Interoperability Hub service list - link to existing services - offer new services from Weblicht	in progress (text extraction service is done)
SRB1	Data-type recognition: TEI, Folia	OEAW, CLARIN/EKUT	Q5 (Jan-Mar 2020), 2PM	with T3.5 (FSD)	TEI, Folia, JSON, done		done

SRB1 +	Including general type determining from header only avoiding large downloads if possible		1PM	Current version copies all the data to the SB storage		Depending on need from services that use large files, for now postponed	
SI1	Ariadne Visual Media Service ⁷⁴	CNR, (tbd)	(tbd)	CNR to propose contribution ARACHNE would also be a prime target for integration	AVS ready, integrated in SB dev version	AVS ready, integrated in SB SSHOC version	done
SI2	Several data conversion services, eg. DDI, TEI, ...	CNR, CLARIN, OEAW		With 3.5 See SD5		SND will additionally provide some conversions	waiting on 3.5
SI3	Dictionaries e.g. Perseus	EKUT, DAI	Q8 (Oct-Dec 2020)	ARACHNE depending on SD1.		Wikipedia, DAI.vocab, DAI. gazetteer, GETTY, FCS integrated and available in SSHOC SB, done waiting for integration in ARACHNE ao.	done, but not all dictionaries useful
SI4	GeoBrowser	UGOE	Q7 (Jun-Sept 2020)	Target catalogue: ARACHNE? discuss with DAI		tested on ARACHNE Gazetteer but Geobrowser is selective wrt KML data-type and does not show proper error message. Discuss with UGOE the proper error handling	done

⁷⁴ The Ariadne Visual Media Service (AVMS) is a service developed at the CNR/IST partner, although from a different group than the one that participates in the SSHOC project work. There is hope for collaboration with the AVMS developers to facilitate integration of the AVMS in the Switchboard but cannot plan accurately.

	Name integration	Responsible	Estimated time/planned date	Status & Comments Sept 2021
SBI1	ARCHE	OEAW	Q5 (Jan-Mar 2020)	done
SBI2	ARACHNE	DAI	Q6 (Apr-Jun 2020)	done
SBI3	DARIAH-DE Repository	UGOE	Q5 (Jan-Mar 2020)	done , to integrate popup version if useful
SBI3	NAKALA	CNR	Q7 (Jun-Sept 2020)	HumaNum: no resources available
SBI4	SSHOC DataVerse	CNR	tbd	done , sustainability extension still too secure
SBI4	PARTHENOS VRE ⁷⁵	CNR	completed, being tested (Feb 2021)	done investigate SB pop-up version integration
SBI5	SND	EKUT	Q8 (Oct-Dec 2020)	With task 3.5 (partner SND) depending on SI2, SD6. Did not find useful data and service combination, postpone until conversion services are available. e.g. DDI to CMDI.

⁷⁵ The PARTHENOS VRE is a result from the PARTHENOS platform and maintained by the CNR/ISTI partner, although from a different group than participates in the SSHOC work. In collaboration with the PARTHENOS VRE maintainers, it is yet to be seen how the current integration can be improved.